

Supporting Materials

To be or not to be a (4,4) net: Reactions of 4'-{4-(*N,N*-diethylaminophenyl)}- and 4'-{4-(*N,N*-diphenylaminophenyl)}-3,2':6',3''- and 4,2':6',4''-terpyridines with cobalt(II) thiocyanate

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Figure S1. MALDI mass spectrum of **1**.

Figure S2. MALDI mass spectrum of **2**.

Data: 023 without matrix_0001_K3_(Manual) 08 June 2022 15:09:07 Cal: Custom Calibration by user1 on 08 June 2022 15:08:08 (Original)
Shimadzu MALDI-8020: Tuning Linear, Power 15, P.Ext at 200.00 (bin 36), Ion Gate Blanking: 1.00
Processed data (averaged): 42.4 mV (um): 8492.5 mV (Um): Unsmoothed, profiles # 1 - 200

Figure S3. MALDI mass spectrum of **3**.

Figure S4. Solid-state IR spectrum of **1**.

Figure S5. Solid-state IR spectrum of **2**.

Figure S6. Solid-state IR spectrum of **3**.

Figure S7. Solid-state IR spectrum of **4**.

Figure S8. ^1H NMR spectrum of **1** (500 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 . Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S9. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of **1** (126 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = CDCl_3 . Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S10. HMQC spectrum of **1** (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 (^1H) or CDCl_3 (^{13}C). Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S11. HMBC spectrum of **1** (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 (^1H) or CDCl_3 (^{13}C). Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S12. ^1H NMR spectrum of **2** (500 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 . Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S13. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of **2** (126 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = CDCl_3 . Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S14. HMQC spectrum of **2** (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 . Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S15. HMBC spectrum of **2** (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 . Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S16. ^1H NMR spectrum of **3** (500 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 . Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S17. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of **3** (126 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = CDCl_3 . Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S18. HMQC spectrum of **3** (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 (^1H) or CDCl_3 (^{13}C). Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S19. HMBC spectrum of **3** (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 (^1H) or CDCl_3 (^{13}C). Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S20. Structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{1})]_n \cdot 0.8n\text{CHCl}_3$ with symmetry generated atoms. Ellipsoids are plotted at the 40% probability level. Solvent molecules and H atoms are omitted for clarity. The ring containing N1 and the NEt_2 unit are disordered and only the major occupancy sites are shown. Symmetry codes: i = $-x, 2-y, 1-z$; ii = $-1/2-x, 1/2+y, 1/2-z$; iii = $1/2-x, -1/2+y, 3/2-z$; iv = $1/2-x, 1/2+y, 3/2-z$; v = $-1/2+x, 3/2-y, -1/2+z$.

Figure S21. Structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{3})]_n \cdot 2n\text{CHCl}_3$ with symmetry generated atoms. Ellipsoids are plotted at the 40% probability level. Solvent molecules and H atoms are omitted for clarity. Symmetry codes: $i = 2-x, 2-y, 1-z$; $ii = 3/2-x, 1/2+y, 1/2-z$; $iii = 5/2-x, -1/2+y, 3/2-z$; $iv = 5/2-x, 1/2+y, 3/2-z$; $v = -1/2+x, 3/2-y, -1/2+z$.

Figure S22. Structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{4})]_n$ with symmetry generated atoms. Ellipsoids are plotted at the 40% probability level, and H atoms are omitted for clarity. Symmetry codes: i = $1-x, 1-y, 1-z$; ii = $1-x, -1/2+y, 1/2-z$; iii = $1-x, 1/2+y, 3/2-z$; iv = $x, 3/2-y, -1/2+z$; v = $1-x, -1/2-y, 3/2+z$

Figure S23. Solid-state FT-IR spectrum of the bulk sample of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{1})]_n \cdot 0.8n\text{CHCl}_3$.

Figure S24. Solid-state FT-IR spectrum of the bulk sample of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{3})]_n \cdot 2n\text{CHCl}_3$.

Figure S25. Solid-state FT-IR spectrum of the bulk sample of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{4})]_n$.

Figure S26. PXRD (CuK α 1 radiation) patterns for $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{1})]_n \cdot 0.8n\text{CHCl}_3$. The experimental data (red circles) are compared with the best fit from the Rietveld refinement analysis (black line). Bragg peak positions (green) and differences between the calculated and experimental plots (blue) are also displayed.

Figure S27. PXRD (CuK α 1 radiation) patterns for $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{3})]_n \cdot 2n\text{CHCl}_3$. The experimental data (red circles) are compared with the best fit from the Rietveld refinement analysis (black line). Bragg peak positions (green) and differences between the calculated and experimental plots (blue) are also displayed.

Figure S28. PXRD (CuK α 1 radiation) patterns for [Co(NCS) $_2$ (**4**)] $_n$. The experimental data (red circles) are compared with the best fit from the Rietveld refinement analysis (black line). Bragg peak positions (green) and differences between the calculated and experimental plots (blue) are also shown.

Figure S29. Structure of [Co(NCS) $_2$ (**2**) $_2$ (MeOH) $_2$] \cdot 3CHCl $_3$ with solvent molecules omitted. H atoms are also omitted for clarity. Ellipsoids are plotted at a 40% probability level. Symmetry code $i = 2-x, -y, 1-z$.

Figure S30. Solid-state FT-IR spectrum of the bulk sample of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{2})_2(\text{MeOH})_2] \cdot 3\text{CHCl}_3$.

Figure S31. PXRD ($\text{CuK}\alpha_1$ radiation) patterns for $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{2})_2(\text{MeOH})_2] \cdot 3\text{CHCl}_3$. The experimental data (red circles) are matched to the best fit from the Rietveld refinement analysis (black line). Bragg peak positions (green) and differences between the calculated and experimental plots (blue) are also shown.